

Molecular Connectors Boosting the Performance of MoS₂ Cathodes in Zinc Ion Batteries

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Zinc-ion batteries (ZIBs) are promising energy storage systems due to their high energy density, low-cost, and the abundant availability of zinc as a raw material. However, the greatest challenge in ZIBs research is the lack of suitable cathode materials that could reversibly intercalate Zn²⁺ ions. Two-dimensional layered materials, especially MoS₂-based, have attracted tremendous interest due to their large surface area and their ability to intercalate/deintercalate ions. Unfortunately, pristine MoS₂ obtained by traditional protocols like chemical exfoliation or hydrothermal/solvothermal methods exhibits limited electronic conductivity and poor chemical stability upon charge/discharge cycling. Here, we report a novel molecular strategy to boost the electrochemical performance of MoS₂ cathode materials for aqueous ZIBs. The use of dithiolated conjugated molecular pillars, i.e. 4,4'-biphenyldithiols, enables to heal defects and crosslink the MoS₂ nanosheets yielding covalently bridged networks (MoS₂-SH₂) with improved ionic and electronic conductivity as well as electrochemical performance. In particular, MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes display high specific capacity of 271.3 mAh×g⁻¹ at 0.1 A×g⁻¹, high energy density of 279 Wh×kg⁻¹, and high power density of 12.3 kW×kg⁻¹. With its outstanding rate capability (capacity of 148.1 mAh×g⁻¹ at 10 A×g⁻¹) and stability (capacity of 179 mAh×g⁻¹ after 1000 cycles), MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes outperform other MoS₂-based electrodes in ZIBs.

1. Introduction

Zinc-ion batteries (ZIBs) are emerging energy storage devices that employ zinc ions as the primary charge carriers.¹⁻⁹ Such batteries possess several notable advantages, including the high theoretical capacity of Zn ($820 \text{ mAh} \times \text{g}^{-1}$), ease of material handling, improved safety, *i.e.*, lower risk of thermal runaway, compared to the lithium-ion batteries, cost-effectiveness, high abundance of Zn resource (like ZnO and ZnS), and compatibility with environmentally benign aqueous electrolytes.¹⁻⁹ However, a few challenges need to be addressed in order to render ZIBs competitive with the currently market-dominating technologies (*i.e.*, lithium-ion batteries), including the identification of suitable cathode materials displaying high capacity, reversibility in the zinc-ion intercalation, and long-term stability.¹⁰ Among the well-known cathode materials, vanadium-based oxides,¹¹ manganese-based oxides,¹² and Prussian blue analogues,¹³ have been explored for ZIBs. Unfortunately, these transition metal oxides are expensive, based on critical raw materials (CRM), exhibit high resistivity and either poor cyclability or limited specific capacity. Therefore, the design of novel electrode materials for Zn storage is highly sought after.

Among the different alternatives, two-dimensional (2D) layered materials have attracted tremendous interest during the past several decades due to their exceptional chemical and physical properties.^{8, 14-16} In particular, the enhanced ion transfer combined with the efficient and reversible ion intercalation/deintercalation resulting from the layered structure held together by weak van der Waals' forces, made 2D layered materials highly suitable electrodes' materials for energy storage applications.¹⁷⁻²¹ Moreover, these materials possess large surface area, which enables optimal exposure of (redox) active sites, *e.g.*, sulphur atoms for MoS₂ or C=O moieties for reduced graphene oxide. Beyond graphene, whose production still mainly relies on the use of natural graphite, which is classified as a CRM, a wide variety of 2D materials,²²⁻²⁴ including layered transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), have been made available. TMDs, which comprise transition metal (M) and chalcogen (X) atoms, are often regarded as inorganic analogues to graphite. MoS₂, being perhaps the most prominent member of the TMDs family, can act as pseudocapacitor, as it can coordinate electrolyte ions *via* a double layer capacitive mechanism as well as *via* Faradic charge transfer processes on the redox active Mo sites.²⁵ However, despite the sufficient interlayer spacing (*i.e.*, 0.62 nm) that should be sufficient to accommodate Zn²⁺ ions (*i.e.*, 0.404-0.43 nm, this range considers the hydrated ionic radius of Zn²⁺), in most reported studies the

pristine MoS₂ cathode material displayed a limited Zn²⁺ storage capacity (approximately 10-40 mAh×g⁻¹).⁴

MoS₂-based cathode materials for ZIBs suffer from three primary drawbacks: low electronic conductivity, significant volume change during the process of intercalation/deintercalation of ions and limited Zn²⁺ ions migration on the basal plane of the 2D material due to the presence of defects, thereby lowering the ionic conductivity of MoS₂.^{4-6, 20} These shortcomings severely limit the electrochemical performance and chemical stability of the ZIBs, leading to small capacity, low rate capability and poor long-term cyclability.^{19, 26} To tackle such relevant problem, four different modification strategies have been pursued including, interlayer engineering, defect engineering, hybridization, and phase engineering.^{4, 27} For instance, M. Sadeeq Balogun and co-workers conducted research on enhancing MoS₂ performance for sodium- and potassium-ion batteries by creating a 3D conductive framework.²⁸ They used titanium nitride nanowires (TiN) coated on 3D carbon fiber (CF) to address MoS₂'s conductivity issues, by improving electronic and ionic transport. The CF@TiN/MoS₂ hybrid achieved notable areal capacities of 5.40 mAh×cm⁻² for sodium storage and 3.29 mAh×cm⁻² for potassium storage, which can be attributed to the enhanced kinetics and direct contact between the active material and Na-ion.²⁸ In another study, a hybrid heterojunction was formed by hydrothermally growing MoS₂ nanosheets on robust titanium-based transition metal compounds, denoted as TNC@MoS₂.²⁷ The TNC@MoS₂ electrodes exhibited impressive rate performance of 200 mAh×g⁻¹ at 50 mA×g⁻¹ and demonstrated cycling stability exceeding 3000 cycles, benefiting from the heterostructure architecture and electric-field effect. Among the other strategies, interlayer engineering is particularly appealing as it allows simultaneously to expand the interlayer spacing and to stabilize the TMDs structures thereby minimizing potential volume fluctuations.²⁷ Differently, interlayer engineering is particularly appealing as it allows simultaneously to expand the interlayer spacing and to stabilize the TMDs structures thereby minimizing potential volume fluctuations. While the use of multiple intercalants has been reported for the interlayer engineering of TMDs, their application for energy storage is still in its infancy. As intercalants, different heteroatoms (*e.g.*, O-doping),⁵ ions (*e.g.*, alkali metals and transition metals)²⁹ and organic/polymeric compounds (*e.g.*, poly(ethylene oxide)³⁰ or polyacrylamide²) have been explored to increase the interlayer distance in MoS₂, achieving an enhanced Zn-storage capacity and reduced Zn²⁺ migration barriers.⁴ Unfortunately, enhancing the interlayer spacing and concurrently improving the electronic

conductivity and unlocking the potential of the basal plane of MoS₂ to boost its electrochemical performance is still a major challenge.

Recently, we have demonstrated that dithiolated conjugated molecules can be used to heal sulfur vacancies and covalently bridge MoS₂ nanosheets to form a network structure, exhibiting enhanced electronic conductivity and excellent physicochemical properties.³¹ We foresee that this molecular strategy can be extended to energy storage applications and will solve the main bottlenecks of the MoS₂-based cathode materials for ZIBs.³²⁻³⁵ The use of conformationally rigid dithiolated conjugated molecular pillars enables to increase the interlayer distance between adjacent MoS₂ nanosheets. The covalent anchoring of adjacent MoS₂ shall prevent any volume changes during the intercalation/deintercalation of ions, therefore enhancing the chemical stability and the long-term cyclability of MoS₂ cathodes. Owing to the π -conjugated structure of these molecules, the interlayer transfer of electrons should be facilitated, improving the electronic conductivity and rate capability of MoS₂ cathodes. Additionally, the tethering of the thiol headgroups to the structural defects of MoS₂ during the synthesis process (*i.e.*, sulfur vacancies) should determine a defect healing which leads to an enhanced intralayer electronic and ionic conductivity of the material, ultimately boosting its electrochemical performance.

Herein, we describe a proof-of-concept of this novel molecular approach for the fabrication of MoS₂-based cathode materials, where MoS₂ nanosheets are covalently interconnected by 4,4'-biphenyldithiol molecules, yielding MoS₂-SH2. We demonstrate that the ZIBs with MoS₂-SH2 cathode materials possess enhanced performance when compared to devices comprising pristine MoS₂ in terms of electronic conductivity (109.2 vs 55.47 S×m⁻¹), ionic conductivity (0.95 vs 0.17 S×m⁻¹), specific capacity (271.3 vs 150 mAh×g⁻¹ at 0.1 A×g⁻¹), rate capability (148.1 vs 40.5 mAh×g⁻¹ at 10 A×g⁻¹), and cycling stability (179 mAh×g⁻¹ after 1000 charge/discharge cycles at 4 A×g⁻¹). Finally, *ex situ* X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis together with high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) made it possible to elucidate the charge storage mechanism of the MoS₂-based electrodes.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis and structural characterization

MoS₂-SH2 nanosheets are synthesized *via* a hydrothermal method under N₂ atmosphere. As illustrated in **Figure 1a**, 4,4'-biphenyldithiol is dissolved in the reaction solution containing

ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate ((NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄) and thiourea (NH₂CSNH₂) under inert atmosphere. The solution is then heated at 180 °C in a Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave for 24 hours. The same experimental procedure is followed for the synthesis of MoS₂ nanosheets but in the absence of 4,4'-biphenyldithiol (Figure 1a). Sulfur vacancies are known to form during the hydrothermal process.^{36, 37} However, in the presence of an excess of 4,4'-biphenyldithiol, those defects are subsequently healed. Furthermore, the molecular design characterized by the two thiol headgroups facilitates the bridging of adjacent MoS₂ nanosheets forming a covalent network.

The morphology and microstructure of MoS₂ (Figure S1) and MoS₂-SH₂ (Figure 1) are investigated by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The SEM and TEM images in Figure 1b-d and Figure S1a-c, for MoS₂-SH₂ and MoS₂, respectively, reveal that the as-prepared materials have a nanosheets morphology (size ~300 nm and thickness ~20 nm) with no significant differences observed between them. High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images (Figure 1e and S1d) display a layered structure of MoS₂-based materials with a lattice spacing of 0.67 nm (MoS₂-SH₂) and 0.66 nm (MoS₂), corresponding to the d-spacing of (002) planes. The mapping analyses from energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy (Figure 1f-i and S1e-h) clearly show the uniform distribution of Mo, S, and C elements in MoS₂-SH₂ and MoS₂.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the synthetic route of MoS₂-SH₂, (b-c) SEM images, (d-e) TEM and HRTEM images and (f-i) SEM image and corresponding element mapping spectra of Mo, S, and C of MoS₂-SH₂.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the MoS₂-SH₂ and MoS₂ nanosheets are presented in **Figure 2a**. MoS₂ nanosheets exhibit a sharp diffraction peak at $2\theta=13.32^\circ$, which originates from the spacing between the layers of (200) plane. The peak at $2\theta=13.12^\circ$ in MoS₂-SH₂ nanosheets shows minimal variation, suggesting that 4,4'-biphenyldithiol hardly alters the lattice spacing, maintaining it at 0.67 nm compared to 0.66 nm in MoS₂ nanosheets, in full agreement with HRTEM analysis. Importantly, this interlayer spacing should be sufficient for the Zn²⁺ ions intercalation/deintercalation.

The Raman spectra of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ nanosheets (Figure 2b) are characterized by the typical E_{12g} and A_{1g} bands. The main differences observed include a slight blue shift of the E_{12g} and A_{1g} peaks, from 382.33 and 407.79 cm⁻¹ (MoS₂) to 383.64 and 408.43 cm⁻¹ (MoS₂-SH₂), as well as the intensity ratio of the E_{12g}/A_{1g} peaks increases from 0.49 in MoS₂ to 0.56 in MoS₂-SH₂. These changes can primarily be attributed to the reduction in the sulfur defect density upon healing with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol.³¹

To gain insight into the chemical states of the materials, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is then performed. The analysis of S2p spectra (Figure 2c-d) reveal two main peaks at 162.4 and 163.7 eV, assigned to the S2p_{3/2} and S2p_{1/2} components, respectively. An additional substoichiometric component can be deconvoluted at 161.5 eV and it is ascribed to defects (*e.g.*, sulfur vacancies).³¹ The area of this component decreases from 7.34 % to 3.61% upon functionalization of the MoS₂ nanosheets with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol, evidencing the efficient healing of the S vacancies. Figure 2e-f show the Mo3d spectra, where the dominant components are the doublet peak located at 231.91 and 228.36 eV, which can be assigned to the Mo 3d_{3/2} and Mo 3d_{5/2} of 1T-MoS₂, respectively. A second doublet peak is located at 232.8 and 229.7 eV, and it can be attributed to the Mo 3d_{3/2} and Mo 3d_{5/2} of 2H-MoS₂, respectively. Therefore, both 1T-MoS₂ and 2H-MoS₂ phases coexist in MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ nanosheets. Previous studies have highlighted the significant advantages of incorporating the metallic 1T phase in MoS₂-based electrodes, as it positively impacts the overall electrochemical performance.³⁸ Interestingly, an additional peak located at 234.6 eV is observed for MoS₂ nanosheets due to the oxidation of Mo⁴⁺ to Mo⁶⁺ under air (Figure 2e), revealing the lower chemical stability of pristine MoS₂.¹⁸

The hydrophilicity of the different samples is quantified by water contact angle (C.A.) measurements (Figure S2). In agreement with previous reports, the C.A. of MoS₂ nanosheets amounts to 56.2°, which after functionalization with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol increases to 75.1°.³⁹

To gain a greater insight into the electrical performance of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂, thin film conductivity measurements are then performed. Pallets of both materials are prepared (see Experimental Section), and the film resistivity is measured with a four-point probe (FPP). The electronic conductivity of the MoS₂ material amounts to be $55.47 \pm 4.33 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$. Importantly, upon functionalization with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol, the electronic conductivity significantly enhances to $109.20 \pm 7.20 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$, i.e. nearly twice the electronic conductivity of MoS₂.

Figure 2. (a) XRD pattern of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂, (b) Raman spectra of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂, (c-f) high-resolution XPS spectra for (c) S2p of MoS₂, (d) S2p of MoS₂-SH₂, (e) Mo3d of MoS₂ and (f) Mo3d of MoS₂-SH₂.

2.2. Electrochemical analysis

Before conducting the electrochemical characterization, the electrolyte's impact on the solubility of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ electrode materials is evaluated. Figure S3 demonstrates that even after immersing these materials in a 4 M zinc (II) trifluoromethanesulfonate solution for three hours, no observable solubility of the materials is detected. To assess the electrochemical performance of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ nanosheets, a zinc ion battery is constructed by utilizing MoS₂ or MoS₂-SH₂ deposited on carbon cloth as cathodes, zinc metal as anode and 4 M zinc(II) trifluoromethanesulfonate as aqueous electrolyte. The cyclic voltammetry (CV) profiles of the MoS₂-SH₂ and MoS₂ electrodes at a scan rate of 0.1 V×s⁻¹ in the voltage range of 0.3-1.5 V are shown in **Figure 3a** and Figure S4a, respectively. Both profiles are dominated by one pair of reduction/oxidation peaks located at 0.62/1.34 V, attributed to the Zn²⁺ intercalation/deintercalation processes. Another pair of reduction/oxidation peaks can also be seen at 0.39/1.18 V, attributed to the H⁺ uptake/release, in great agreement with reported mechanistic investigations.⁴⁰ The first three cycles of MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes reveal no significant changes in the current density or any change in the shape of the CV curves, suggesting a highly reversible nature of the intercalation/deintercalation processes. However, for the MoS₂ electrodes, there is an obvious peak shift in the first three cycles, indicating its low reversibility and the possible occurrence of irreversible structural changes upon Zn²⁺ intercalation.

To shed light onto the nature of the charge storage mechanism of MoS₂-based materials, the kinetics of the electrochemical processes occurring at both electrode materials is determined by exploiting the procedure proposed by Wu *et al.*, (see Figure S5).⁴¹ The relation of the peak current (*i*) and scan rate (*v*) from CV complies with the equation:

$$i = av^b. \quad (1)$$

where *a* and *b* are adjustable parameters. Typically, the coefficient *b* falls within the range of 0.5 to 1.0. A *b*-value of 0.5 indicates a diffusion-limited electrochemical process, while a *b*-value of 1.0 suggests a capacitive-limited process. The average values of *b* for MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ are 0.86 and 0.65, respectively. While both materials can be considered hybrid, as there is the coexistence of an electrical double layer (EDL) and battery-type mechanism, a predominantly capacitive-controlled contribution in the charge storage mechanism is obtained for MoS₂. Interestingly, upon the functionalization of MoS₂ with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol, the contribution of the

diffusion-controlled in the charge storage mechanism increases, as a result of the bigger and well-controlled interlayer distance between the MoS₂ nanosheets.

To further analyze the capacitive contribution and the diffusion-controlled contribution at a specific scan rate, the eq. (1) can be divided into two components, as shown below:

$$i = k_1v + k_2v^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where k_1v and $k_2v^{1/2}$ represent the capacitive and diffusion limited effects, respectively. The capacitive and diffusion-controlled capacity values at different rates are calculated and shown in Figure S5e-f for MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂, respectively and Figures S6-7. As shown in Figure S5f and S7 the diffusion contribution to the charge storage mechanism for the MoS₂-SH₂ is the highest (63.62%) at the lowest scan rate (0.1 V×s⁻¹). The capacitive contribution gradually increases with the scan rate for both MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂. Therefore, the presence of both capacitive and diffusion-controlled charge storage mechanisms confirms the hybrid nature of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ materials, which offer significant advantages for energy storage.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data is analyzed using Nyquist plots (Figure 3b) and the experimental results are well fitted with the indicated circuit (Figure S8). The magnitude of the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) decreases from 118 Ω (MoS₂ electrodes) to 21 Ω (MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes) providing evidence for the higher electronic conductivity and rate capability of functionalized MoS₂ network. Alongside, the ionic conductivity increases from 0.17 S×m⁻¹ (MoS₂ electrodes) to 0.95 S×m⁻¹ (MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes).

The galvanostatic charge/discharge (GCD) profiles of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes at a current density of 1 A×g⁻¹ are shown in Figures S4b and 3c, respectively. In full agreement with the CV analysis, the GCD profiles of both materials reveal plateaus at the same voltages where the Zn²⁺ intercalation/deintercalation processes occur. At a current density of 1 A×g⁻¹ the MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes can deliver a highly reversible capacity of 225.6 mAh×g⁻¹, with high coulombic efficiency (about 100 %) over 200 cycles (Figure 3d). Conversely, during the first 15 cycles, the capacity of MoS₂ electrodes gradually increases. The increase in capacity observed in MoS₂ during the initial cycles can be attributed to several factors, including the activation processes, surface reconfiguration, and the formation of surface defects that enhance its electrochemical performance. The low coulombic efficiency reveals that the number of active storage sites is increasing during cycling, and it is also associated with the expansion of layered structure.^{5, 17} Nevertheless, this increased capacity is accompanied by a drawback, wherein the process of ion intercalation and

deintercalation induces substantial volume alterations within the structure of MoS₂. These volume changes result in mechanical stress, which eventually leads to structural degradation and loss of active surface area. Consequently, the capacity of MoS₂ electrodes decreases sharply to 64.5 mAh×g⁻¹ in subsequent cycles due to the structural damage incurred, limiting the material's ability to maintain the enhanced capacitance observed during the initial cycles. The functionalization of MoS₂ with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol molecules represents an effective strategy to circumvent these volume changes, thereby enhancing the chemical stability of MoS₂ during charge and discharge cycles.

MoS₂-SH2 electrodes also exhibit an outstanding rate capability compared to the MoS₂ electrodes and to other MoS₂-based cathode materials for ZIBs (see Table S1). As shown in Figure 3f, MoS₂-SH2 electrodes deliver very high specific capacities of 271.3, 263.3, 234.0, 218.8, 195.3, 174.7, and 148.1 mAh×g⁻¹ at current densities of 0.1, 0.2, 1, 2, 4, 8, and 10 A×g⁻¹, respectively. The GCD profiles of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH2 electrodes at different current densities can be seen in Figure S9. Furthermore, an average capacity of 233.2 mAh×g⁻¹ could still be achieved when the current density is decreased down to 1 A×g⁻¹. Impressively, at a high current density of 4 A×g⁻¹, the MoS₂-SH2 electrodes can deliver a very high specific capacity about 179.4 mAh×g⁻¹ with a capacity retention of 88.5 % after 1000 cycles (Figure 3e).

The energy and power density of MoS₂-SH2 ZIB are plotted in Figure 3g, showing that the highest energy density achieved amounts to 279 Wh×kg⁻¹ thereby outperforming all the other MoS₂-based cathode materials for ZIBs (See Table S1 and Figure 3g). Additionally, the highest power density achieved for MoS₂-SH2 corresponds to 12.3 kW×kg⁻¹, being among the state-of-the-art values for other cathode materials reported for ZIBs.

As shown in Table S2, the enhanced electrochemical performance of MoS₂-SH2 aligns with all the reported physical characteristics relevant for energy storage applications. The healing of defects in MoS₂ by 4,4'-biphenyldithiol not only led to increased electronic and ionic conductivity but also contributed to enhanced chemical stability during the Zn ion intercalation and deintercalation. By and large, the functionalization of MoS₂ with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol remarkably improved the electrochemical performance of the pristine MoS₂ material.

Figure 3. (a) Cyclic voltammogram curve of MoS₂-SH₂, (b) Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ (c) charge-discharge profiles of MoS₂-SH₂, (d) cycling

performance of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ at 1 A×g⁻¹, (e) long-term cycling performance of MoS₂-SH₂ at 4 A×g⁻¹, (f) rate performance of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ at various current densities, (g) Ragone plot for MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ and other cathode materials for ZIBs. The references of the materials in the Ragone plot can be found in the Supporting Information, Table S1.

2.3. Charge storage mechanism and post-mortem analysis

Ex situ XRD characterization is performed to elucidate the reaction mechanism of the MoS₂-SH₂ and MoS₂ electrodes (**Figure 4**). The marked states at the GCD profile (points A-I) are selected for the *ex situ* XRD analyses (Figure 4). For MoS₂ electrodes (Figure 4a-b), the (002) peak shifts from 13.32° to 12.60° during the discharging process, suggesting that the interlayer distance expanded from 0.66 nm to 0.70 nm due to the intercalation of Zn²⁺ ions. During the charging process, the (002) peak and interlayer distance are recovered to their initial values. Conversely, there is no obvious shift of the (002) peak for MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes during the discharging/recharging processes (Figure 4 c-d), indicating that there are no relevant structural changes associated with the Zn²⁺ ions intercalation/deintercalation.

Thus, the possible electrochemical reactions between the MoS₂-based cathode materials and Zn anode can be summarized as below (Figure S10):²

In addition, *ex situ* HRTEM images further demonstrate that the interlayer distance of the fully discharged MoS₂ electrodes expands from 0.66 nm to 0.70 nm and decreases back to 0.66 nm when the electrodes are fully recharged (Figure 4 e-g). Differently, the interlayer distance for MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes, in full agreement with *ex situ* XRD analysis, remains constant (0.67 nm) without any expansion during the discharging/recharging processes (Figure 4 h-j).

Figure S11 shows the *ex situ* SEM images of the fully charged and fully discharged MoS₂-SH₂ (Figure S11a-b) and MoS₂ (Figure S11c-d) electrodes after 1000 cycles. While MoS₂-SH₂ nanosheets still retains its 2D layered structure, MoS₂ nanosheets are largely agglomerated, indicating that the MoS₂-SH₂ nanosheets functionalized with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol have a superior

chemical stability compared to pristine MoS₂ nanosheets.

Figure 4. (a) Charge/discharge profiles of pristine MoS₂ for the second cycle, (b) *ex situ* XRD patterns of MoS₂ performed at marked states of A-H, (c) charge/discharge profiles of MoS₂-SH₂ for the second cycle, (d) *ex situ* XRD patterns of MoS₂-SH₂ performed at marked states of A-H, (e-g) *ex situ* HRTEM for MoS₂ of (e) pristine MoS₂, (f) fully discharged MoS₂, (g) fully charged MoS₂, (h-j) *ex situ* HRTEM for MoS₂-SH₂ of (h) pristine MoS₂-SH₂, (i) fully discharged MoS₂-SH₂, (j) fully charged MoS₂-SH₂.

Then, *ex situ* X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses are performed in the pristine, discharged (at 0.3 V) and charged (at 1.5 V) states of MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ (Figure S12-12). The high-resolution Zn2p spectra (Figure S12b, d) revealed the typical peaks at 1021 and 1044 eV of Zn²⁺, in the discharged state as a consequence of their intercalation in the MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes along with some surface adsorption. Upon recharging to 1.5 V, one pair of weak Zn signals is still observed owing to the residual Zn-electrolyte adsorption or the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) formation.⁵ The deconvoluted Mo3d XPS spectra of MoS₂ and MoS₂-

SH2 reveal that the pristine electrode materials contain 67.06% 1T-phase and 26.19% 2H-phase for MoS₂ (Figure S13a and Table S3) and 68.42% 1T-phase and 15.29% 2H-phase for MoS₂-SH2 (Figure S13b and Table S4). After discharging to 0.3 V, the 2H-phase content increases in both cases (Tables S3-4), accompanied by an increase of Mo⁶⁺ content. The intercalation and deintercalation of Zn²⁺ ions into the MoS₂ lattice led to changes in its structure. The 2H phase of MoS₂ is more favorable for the accommodation of zinc ions due to its relatively larger interlayer spacing compared to the 1T phase. As a result, the MoS₂ tends to transform more into the 2H phase upon discharging in zinc ion batteries to accommodate the inserted zinc ions. When charged to 1.5 V, the almost restored 1T-phase proportion confirms the reversible phase transition between 2H- and 1T-MoS₂ upon cycling. As evident from Tables 3-4, the reversibility is notably enhanced with MoS₂-SH2, wherein the incorporation of 4,4'-biphenyldithiol contributes to enhancing the chemical stability of MoS₂. Consequently, this reinforcement results in greater structural resilience of MoS₂ during ion intercalation and deintercalation processes. Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy mapping images reveal the uniform distribution of Mo, S, and Zn elements within the fully discharged electrodes (Figures S14-15), confirming the successful Zn²⁺ intercalation. When the electrodes are charged to 1.5 V, the fuzzy Zn outline can still be detected because of the surface electrolyte adsorption or the SEI formation.

3. Conclusions

In summary, we have reported an unprecedented molecular strategy for the fabrication of MoS₂-based electrodes exhibiting enhanced electrochemical performance in zinc ion batteries. We have demonstrated that the use of a dithiolated conjugated molecule (*i.e.*, 4,4'-biphenyldithiol) as an organic linker offers multiple advantages compared to pristine MoS₂. For example, MoS₂-SH2 revealed an enhanced ionic conductivity (0.95 S×m⁻¹) and electronic conductivity (109.20 ± 7.20 S×m⁻¹) due to the reduction of sulfur vacancies and to the facilitated interlayer electron transfer. The covalent functionalization of MoS₂ nanosheets with 4,4'-biphenyldithiol not only expanded the interlayer distances of MoS₂ nanosheets (0.67 nm), facilitating the intercalation of Zn²⁺ ions, but also improved the chemical stability and long-term cyclability of MoS₂-SH2 electrodes. *Ex situ* XRD and HRTEM analysis confirmed the stability of the interlayer distance and the absence of significant structural changes associated with the Zn²⁺ ions intercalation/deintercalation. In

terms of electrochemical performance, MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes showed a desirable specific capacity of 271.3 mAh×g⁻¹ at 0.1 A×g⁻¹ and a specific energy density of 279 Wh×kg⁻¹, and power density of 12.3 kW×kg⁻¹. Such key performance indicators are superior to the state of the art of ZIBs integrating MoS₂-based electrodes. Impressively, the rate capability of MoS₂-SH₂ electrodes (capacity of 148.1 mAh×g⁻¹ at 10 A×g⁻¹) is much higher than other MoS₂-based electrodes in ZIBs. Additionally, this battery also exhibited a good long-term cyclic stability, over 88.54 % capacity retention could be obtained with a specific capacity about 179 mAh×g⁻¹ at a high current density of 4 A×g⁻¹ after 1000 cycles. Overall, this work paves the way for the rational design of other MoS₂-based electrodes using a molecular strategy to achieve outstanding electrochemical performance in electronic devices and energy-related applications.

4. Experimental methods

4.1. Synthesis of pristine MoS₂ and MoS₂-SH₂

Ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate ((NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O, 1.35 g) and thiourea (NH₂CSNH₂, 2.51 g) were dissolved in 35 mL distilled water with N₂ gas plugged in. Then, 4,4'-biphenyldithiol (C₁₂H₁₀S₂, 0.15 g) was added into the solution before transferred into a 50 mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave. And the autoclave was sealed and heated at 180 °C for 24 h before cooling down to room temperature naturally. The MoS₂-SH₂ nanosheets sample was obtained finally after washing with distilled water and ethanol for several times. For comparison, pristine MoS₂ nanosheets were prepared using the same methodology but without the addition of 4,4'-biphenyldithiol.

4.2. Material Characterization:

All chemicals and solvents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and TCI used as received without any purification.

The **X-ray powder diffraction (XRD)** patterns were carried out by Bruker D8 X-ray diffractometer. **X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)** measurements were employed with a Thermo Scientific K-alpha spectrometer with an aluminum X-ray source (1.4866 keV energy), working at a vacuum level of 10⁻⁸-10⁻⁹ mbar in the main chamber. All XPS spectra were calibrated using the C 1s peak (284.8 eV) as a reference. **Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)** images

were investigated with a FEI Quanta FEG 250 instrument S3 (FEI corporate, Hillsboro, Oregon, USA). **High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM)** was carried out with a JEOL 2100F microscope working at 200 kV, equipped with a Cs probe corrector and a GATAN Tridiem imaging filter. **Raman** spectra were acquired with a Renishaw InVia Reflex system. The spectrograph used a high-resolution grating (2400 grooves cm^{-1}) with additional bandpass filter optics, a confocal microscope, and a 2D-CCD camera. The excitation was carried out using a 532 nm laser excitation beam, with a 100 \times objective, 0.2 mW maximum power and 1 s acquisition time. The water contact angle (C.A.) measurements were performed with a Krüss DSA100S instrument by depositing on MoS₂-based films, sessile drops (2 μL) of water (5 different drops per sample). For each sample, the drop images at 30 s were fitted by the Ellipse (Tangent-1) method and the mean values and standard deviation were reported.

4.3.Four-Point Probe measurements. Films resistivities were measured with Jandel, Model RM3000, limit of detection $10^7 \Omega \times \text{sq}^{-1}$. The resistivity (ρ) was obtained

$$\rho = R_s \cdot l \quad (1)$$

Where R_s is the sheet resistance and l is thickness of the film.

4.4.Electrochemical characterization

The electrode was prepared with 70 wt.% of active materials, 20 wt.% of Super P, and 10 wt.% of polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) as the binder coated onto carbon cloth current collector. The electrodes were dried at 80 °C overnight in a vacuum oven. The mass loading for each electrode was $1.5 \text{ mg} \times \text{cm}^{-2}$. Zinc ion batteries were assembled use a 2032 coin cell with zinc foil as anode electrode, 4 M zinc(II) trifluoromethanesulfonate as aqueous electrolyte, and glass fibre as a separator. The cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were carried out on Autolab PGSTAT 128N Potentiostat instrument with a Metrohm Autolab cell holder at room temperature. EIS measurement was employed in the frequency range of 0.01 Hz to 1 MHz. The galvanostatic charge/discharge and rate performance were studied on Neware Battery Tester.

4.5.Calculation of ionic conductivity (σ)

$$\sigma = \frac{l}{R_{ct} \cdot A} \quad (2)$$

Being l the film thickness (10 μm), A the film area (0.5 cm^2) and R_{ct} is the charge transfer resistance.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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